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The Strategy of Social Media Marketing on Skintific's Sales and Brand Image

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Abstract

The advancement of digital technology has brought significant changes to marketing practices in many industries, including the skincare sector. Social media has emerged as a widely used marketing medium because it allows companies to distribute information efficiently, interact directly with consumers, and reach broader audiences compared to traditional promotional channels. This paper aims to examine how social media marketing strategies contribute to increasing sales performance and shaping the brand image of Skintific, a skincare brand that actively utilizes digital platforms in its marketing activities. The discussion highlights several strategies adopted by the company, including content marketing, influencer marketing, live shopping, and consumer engagement through social media platforms. The discussion shows that social media marketing provides various benefits for Skintific. Informative and engaging content helps improve consumer awareness and trust, while collaborations with influencers support product promotion and expand market exposure. Furthermore, digital features such as live shopping, affiliate programs, and e-commerce integration simplify the purchasing process, making it easier for consumers to access and buy products. Social media interactions, positive reviews, and electronic word of mouth (e-WOM) also contribute to creating favorable consumer perceptions and strengthening the company's brand image. Overall, social media marketing plays an important role in supporting sales growth and enhancing Skintific's brand image. The combination of content marketing, influencer marketing, and active communication with consumers enables the company to strengthen customer relationships and remain competitive in the rapidly evolving digital marketplace.

Keywords: social media marketing, Skintific, sales, brand image, content marketing, influencer marketing.

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INTRODUCTION

The development of digital technology has brought about significant changes to corporate marketing activities. Whereas companies previously relied more on conventional media such as television, radio, or brochures for promotion, social media has now become one of the most frequently used platforms for marketing activities. The presence of social media makes it easier for companies to convey product information to the public more quickly and widely. Additionally, social media allows companies to interact directly with consumers through comments, messages, and various other forms of digital content. These factors make social media marketing a crucial strategy for enhancing a company's competitiveness in the digital age (Afifah & Utari, 2024).

The use of social media in marketing is also growing rapidly in the beauty and skincare industry. The public's high interest in skincare products has led skincare companies to increasingly leverage digital platforms to capture consumers' attention. Most consumers, particularly younger generations, now more frequently seek product information through TikTok, Instagram, or influencer reviews before making a purchase. This indicates that social media is not only used as a form of entertainment but has also become a source of information that influences consumers' purchasing decisions. Therefore, skincare companies need to create digital marketing strategies capable of capturing attention and building consumer trust in the products they offer (Riwong & Wono, 2024).

One skincare brand that has been quite active in using social media as a marketing tool is Skintific. In recent years, Skintific has successfully captured public attention through various

promotional content that frequently appears on TikTok and Instagram. The marketing strategy employed involves not only product advertisements but also leveraging influencers, beauty creators, live shopping, and user review content. These pieces of content are created with engaging concepts and follow social media trends, making them more easily accepted by consumers. Through this strategy, Skintific has been able to increase engagement and expand its market reach, particularly among Gen Z and millennials who actively use social media in their daily lives (Martiza & Furqon, 2024).

In addition to leveraging content marketing, Skintific also uses influencer marketing as one of its key strategies for introducing its products to the public. Influencers are considered to have a significant influence on purchasing decisions because consumers tend to trust the experiences and recommendations shared by content creators more than traditional advertisements. Product reviews, skincare tutorials, and testimonials shared by influencers can shape consumers' perceptions of a brand. Many of Skintific's promotional posts have gone viral on TikTok, encouraging people to try the products. This demonstrates that social media plays a significant role in building the popularity of a skincare brand (Riwong & Wono, 2024).

A company's success in leveraging social media not only boosts sales but also influences the formation of brand image. Brand image refers to consumers' views or perceptions of a brand, shaped by their experiences, the information available, and the company's marketing activities. In the skincare industry, brand image is a critical factor because consumers typically prefer products with a good reputation and are trusted to be safe to use. Therefore, companies need to maintain brand image through appropriate marketing strategies to enhance consumer trust in the products offered. Previous studies have shown that social media marketing activities positively influence brand awareness, brand image, and customer loyalty toward Skintific products (Afifah & Utari, 2024).

Besides influencing brand image, social media marketing can also increase company sales. Through social media, companies can promote products more effectively and at relatively lower costs compared to conventional marketing methods. Features such as live streaming, affiliate marketing, and TikTok Shop make it easier for consumers to obtain information and purchase products directly. Attractive promotional content can also enhance consumers' purchase intentions. Research conducted by Hung and Muzammil (2023) revealed that social media marketing and brand image positively influence consumer purchase intention toward Skintific products. This finding indicates that digital marketing strategies are closely related to increasing product sales in today's digital era.

RESEARCH QUESTIONS

Based on these phenomena, it can be observed that social media marketing strategies play an important role in increasing sales and shaping a company's brand image, particularly in the skincare industry. Skintific's success in utilizing social media is worth further investigation because it demonstrates how digital marketing strategies can influence consumer behavior amid increasingly competitive business environments. Therefore, this study seeks to answer the following research questions:

1. How do the social media marketing strategies implemented by Skintific influence product sales?
2. How do the social media marketing strategies implemented by Skintific contribute to the formation of brand image among consumers?

Research Objectives

This study aims:

1. Identify the social media marketing strategies used by Skintific to market its skincare products through social media.
2. Determine the impact of social media marketing on increasing sales of Skintific products.
3. Determine the impact of social media marketing on the formation of Skintific's brand image among consumers.
4. Determine the role of content marketing, influencer marketing, and live shopping in attracting consumer interest in purchasing Skintific products.

5. Determine how social media helps Skintific build relationships and interactions with consumers in the digital age.

THEORETICAL REVIEW

Social Media Marketing

Social media marketing is a digital strategy that uses social media platforms for promotion, communication, and interaction between companies and customers. Advances in digital technology have prompted companies to shift from traditional marketing methods to social media-based methods, as they are considered more efficient in reaching the market. Apps such as TikTok, Instagram, and YouTube have become the top choices for companies to introduce their products to the public quickly and widely. According to research by Oktavia and Mariam (2024), social media marketing has a positive impact on brand image and consumer purchase intent regarding skincare products. While used as a promotional tool, social media marketing also serves to foster closer relationships between companies and customers.

Through these platforms, companies can interact directly with customers via comments, live streams, or direct messages. This interaction helps companies understand customer needs and increase engagement with a specific brand. Content that is engaging and relevant to social media trends can also draw public attention to the products being offered. In the skincare industry, social media marketing is crucial because the majority of consumers search for information about products across various platforms before making a purchase. Consumers typically look at reviews from other users, recommendations from influencers, and product tutorials to ensure the quality of the skincare products they want to buy. Therefore, skincare companies need to make the most of social media to boost sales and strengthen their brand image in the public eye.

Content Marketing

Content marketing is a marketing approach that focuses on creating and distributing valuable, relevant, and useful information to customers. The content may take various forms, such as educational videos, articles, product reviews, tutorials, or information explaining product benefits and usage. The primary objective of content marketing is not only to promote products but also to provide information that can help consumers make better decisions. By consistently delivering content that meets consumers' needs, companies can attract attention, increase engagement, and build long-term relationships with their target audience. In the skincare industry, content marketing has become particularly important because consumers often seek extensive information before deciding to purchase a product. Since skincare products are directly related to skin health, consumers tend to be more selective and careful when evaluating different brands and product options. Therefore, companies need to provide clear, accurate, and trustworthy information that can help consumers understand the value and benefits of the products being offered.

Companies generally create content about the ingredients in skincare products, the benefits offered, how to use them, and skincare tips, so that consumers better understand what they are offering. Educational and engaging content can also increase consumer trust in a particular brand, which in turn can spark interest in purchasing. Research by Morelin and Tunjungsari (2024) shows that visual-based social media marketing has a positive impact on purchase intention and electronic word of mouth (e-WOM) in the skincare industry. Engaging visual content can capture consumers' attention and encourage social media users to share information about the product with others. Therefore, it is important for companies to create innovative content and keep up with digital trends to ensure their marketing strategies are effective.

Influencer Marketing

Influencer marketing is an approach that leverages influential individuals on social media platforms to promote products or services to the public. Individuals who act as influencers are believed to have the ability to influence consumers' purchasing decisions because their followers tend to rely on the experiences and advice they provide. In the skincare sector, this method is frequently used because reviews and testimonials from influencers are perceived as more persuasive than traditional

advertisements. Promotions through influencers are typically conducted via product reviews, tutorials on how to use skincare products, or sharing personal experiences after using a specific product. The content generated helps consumers gain an understanding of a product's quality before they make a purchase.

Additionally, influencers can enhance a product's appeal because they have a large following on social media platforms such as TikTok and Instagram. Research by Wulandari and Respati (2024) reveals that social media marketing involving influencers can increase consumer purchase intent by creating a positive brand image. Consumers are generally more inclined to buy skincare products after seeing recommendations from influencers who are perceived as having knowledge and experience in the beauty field. Therefore, influencer marketing has become a crucial tactic in current digital marketing strategies within the skincare sector.

Brand Image

Brand image refers to consumers' views or perceptions of a brand, which are shaped by their experiences, the information they receive, and the company's marketing activities. A strong brand image can reinforce consumer trust in a product, thereby influencing purchasing decisions. In the skincare sector, brand image is a crucial element because the products directly impact consumers' skin health and safety. Brand image can be built through various marketing methods, one of which is social media. Engaging promotional content, positive user reviews, and recommendations from influencers can foster a positive view of a brand.

On the other hand, negative comments circulating on social media can have a detrimental effect on a company's brand image in the public eye. Therefore, companies must maintain product quality and marketing activities to continue earning consumer trust. Research conducted by Tamara and Masreviastuti (2024) indicates that brand image has a positive and significant impact on the choice of skincare products. The better a product's brand image, the greater the consumer interest in purchasing it. Thus, brand image is a crucial aspect that companies must prioritize to enhance their competitiveness in an increasingly digital business landscape.

Sales

Sales are activities carried out by a company to market and sell products to consumers with the objective of generating revenue and profit. The level of sales achieved by a company is often used as an indicator of how effective its marketing strategies are in reaching target customers. An increase in sales generally reflects higher consumer demand and provides greater opportunities for the company to improve profitability and maintain business continuity. In today's digital era, sales performance is influenced not only by the quality of the products offered but also by how effectively companies utilize digital marketing channels. Changes in consumer behavior have encouraged more people to search for product information, compare alternatives, and make purchases through online platforms. As a result, companies are required to develop marketing strategies that can adapt to these changes and meet evolving consumer needs. Monitoring sales performance is also important because it helps companies evaluate market responses and identify opportunities for future business growth.

Social media allows companies to promote products more quickly and widely through features such as live shopping, affiliate marketing, and digital marketplaces. Consumers can also purchase products immediately after seeing ads that appear on social media. A study by Fitri et al. (2024) shows that social media marketing on TikTok and brand image have a significant influence on purchasing decisions for Skintific skincare products. This indicates that digital marketing strategies can attract consumer interest while driving increased sales of skincare products. Therefore, companies should make optimal use of social media to boost sales and expand their market reach.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

The rapid development of digital technology has significantly changed the way companies carry out marketing activities, including those operating in the skincare industry. Marketing activities that previously relied heavily on conventional media are now increasingly supported by digital platforms, particularly social media. Platforms such as TikTok, Instagram, and YouTube have become important

channels for companies to introduce products, communicate with consumers, and expand market reach. Social media is considered an effective marketing medium because information can be disseminated quickly and accessed by a broad audience. Kotler and Keller (2021) explain that social media has become an essential element of digital marketing as it enables companies to establish more interactive and direct communication with consumers.

The growing use of social media has also influenced consumer behavior in the skincare market. Before purchasing skincare products, consumers generally seek information from various digital sources, including product reviews, skincare tutorials, and recommendations shared by influencers. This behavior is particularly common among Generation Z and millennials, who actively use social media in their daily lives. Recognizing this trend, Skintific has utilized social media as one of its primary marketing channels to increase sales and strengthen brand image. Through consistent digital activities, the company is able to introduce its products to a wider audience while maintaining active engagement with consumers.

One of the strategies implemented by Skintific is content marketing. Through various social media platforms, the company consistently creates content that not only promotes products but also provides educational information related to skincare. The content includes explanations of product ingredients, skincare routines, instructions for product usage, and tips for maintaining healthy skin. This approach provides additional value to consumers because they gain useful information alongside promotional messages. According to Kotler and Keller (2021), content that is relevant, informative, and beneficial can help companies build stronger and longer-term relationships with consumers.

To maximize audience engagement, Skintific also develops promotional content that aligns with current social media trends. Many of its videos are presented in short formats, use popular music, and feature before-and-after concepts that attract viewers' attention. Such content has a greater opportunity to appear on TikTok's For You Page (FYP), enabling the company to reach more potential consumers. The widespread visibility of this content demonstrates how creativity and innovation in content creation contribute to the effectiveness of social media marketing strategies.

Besides content marketing, influencer marketing has become another important component of Skintific's promotional activities. The company collaborates with beauty influencers, content creators, and social media personalities to introduce and review its skincare products. This strategy is considered effective because consumers often perceive influencer recommendations as more authentic and trustworthy than traditional advertising. Reviews shared by influencers usually include personal experiences, product demonstrations, and explanations of skincare benefits, allowing consumers to gain a clearer understanding of the products before making purchasing decisions.

Research conducted by Riwong and Wono (2024) indicates that marketing content distributed through social media can positively influence consumers' perceptions of Skintific. The visibility of product reviews and recommendations from content creators contributes to increasing consumer confidence in product quality. Furthermore, influencers often have large audiences that help brands expand their market reach and improve product exposure. As a result, several Skintific products have gained popularity through extensive promotion on platforms such as TikTok and Instagram.

The effectiveness of social media marketing is not limited to increasing product awareness and sales. It also plays an important role in shaping brand image. Brand image reflects consumers' perceptions of a brand, which are formed through experiences, information, and interactions with marketing activities. In the skincare industry, a positive brand image is particularly important because consumers tend to prefer products that are perceived as safe, reliable, and of good quality.

Through its social media activities, Skintific has successfully established an image as a modern skincare brand that is relevant to the needs of younger consumers. Educational content, attractive visual presentations, and active engagement with users have helped create positive perceptions among consumers. In addition, recommendations and reviews shared by influencers and customers further strengthen public confidence in the brand. Widiyanti and Ramli (2024) state that social media marketing contributes positively to brand image because the information shared through digital platforms influences consumer perceptions and trust toward a brand.

Another factor that strengthens Skintific's brand image is the large number of positive reviews available on social media and online marketplaces. Consumers often evaluate feedback from other users before purchasing skincare products due to concerns regarding product quality and safety. Consequently, electronic word of mouth (e-WOM) has become an important source of information that influences purchasing decisions. Positive reviews that circulate widely online help increase product popularity while reinforcing a favorable brand image.

In addition to enhancing brand image, social media marketing has also contributed to the growth of Skintific's sales performance. Promotional content that becomes viral often generates curiosity among consumers and encourages them to try the products. The availability of digital shopping features such as TikTok Shop, affiliate marketing programs, Shopee, and other e-commerce platforms has simplified the purchasing process, allowing consumers to buy products immediately after viewing promotional content. According to Safira and Aryansyah (2023), social media activities can positively affect consumer interest and loyalty because they help build trust and strengthen consumer engagement with a brand.

Compared with traditional promotional methods, digital marketing also offers broader market coverage. Through social media, companies can reach consumers from different geographical locations without significant limitations. This wider exposure increases opportunities to attract potential customers and generate higher sales. Furthermore, social media marketing is generally more cost-efficient than advertising through television, radio, or print media, making it an attractive option for companies seeking effective promotional strategies.

Despite its benefits, implementing social media marketing also presents several challenges. The skincare industry is highly competitive, requiring companies to continuously create innovative and engaging content to maintain consumer interest. Rapid changes in digital trends also require companies to adapt quickly in order to remain relevant in the market. In addition, companies must consistently maintain product quality and customer satisfaction because negative reviews shared on social media can spread rapidly and potentially damage brand reputation. Widiandi and Ramli (2024) emphasize that social media marketing can influence consumer perceptions, trust, and loyalty, making effective social media management an important factor in maintaining a positive brand image.

Overall, the discussion demonstrates that social media marketing has become a crucial strategy for improving sales performance and strengthening Skintific's brand image. Through the integration of content marketing, influencer marketing, and active interaction on social media platforms, the company is able to build stronger relationships with consumers and enhance its competitiveness in the digital marketplace. Consistent with the findings of Afifah and Utari (2024), social media marketing contributes positively to brand image and customer loyalty because it facilitates closer and more meaningful relationships between companies and consumers.

CONCLUSION

Based on the discussion results regarding "*The Strategy of Social Media Marketing on Skintific's Sales and Brand Image*," it can be concluded that the development of digital technology has transformed corporate marketing patterns, particularly in the skincare industry. Social media is no longer used solely as a medium for communication and entertainment but has also become an effective marketing tool for building relationships between companies and consumers. Platforms such as TikTok, Instagram, and YouTube enable companies to deliver product information quickly, broadly, and interactively. These conditions have made social media marketing one of the primary strategies companies use to enhance business competitiveness in today's digital era.

Skintific has become one of the skincare brands that successfully utilizes social media as an optimal digital marketing strategy. The company has created various promotional contents that are engaging, educational, and aligned with social media trends, making them more appealing to consumers, especially Generation Z and millennials. The marketing strategy implemented focuses not only on product promotion but also on educating consumers about skin health, skincare ingredients, and proper product usage. This educational content provides additional value for consumers because they

gain not only product information but also skincare knowledge. As a result, consumers develop greater trust in the quality and benefits of Skintific products.

In addition to content marketing, Skintific also employs influencer marketing as one of its primary strategies to increase product popularity. Collaborations with beauty influencers, content creators, and social media personalities have proven effective in increasing consumer interest in Skintific skincare products. Influencers are considered highly influential because consumers tend to trust personal experiences and recommendations more than traditional advertisements. Product reviews, skincare tutorials, and testimonials shared by influencers help consumers understand product quality before making purchasing decisions. This demonstrates that influencer marketing plays an important role in shaping positive consumer perceptions toward a brand.

The social media marketing strategy implemented by Skintific has also proven effective in increasing product sales. Viral promotional content on social media encourages public interest and curiosity to try skincare products. Digital features such as live shopping, TikTok Shop, affiliate marketing, and online marketplaces simplify consumers' access to information while enabling direct product purchases. This convenience makes purchasing processes faster and more practical, thereby increasing consumers' purchase intentions. With promotional costs that are relatively lower than traditional marketing methods, social media provides significant advantages for companies in expanding market reach and increasing sales performance.

Besides increasing sales, social media marketing also has a significant impact on building Skintific's brand image. Through social media, Skintific has successfully established itself as a modern, trustworthy, high-quality skincare brand that aligns with the needs of younger generations. Positive reviews from influencers and social media users contribute to increasing consumer trust in Skintific products. Electronic word of mouth (*e-WOM*) shared through TikTok, Instagram, and online marketplaces further strengthens public perceptions of the brand. The more positive experiences consumers share, the stronger the brand image developed in consumers' minds.

However, implementing social media marketing also presents several challenges. The increasingly competitive skincare industry requires companies to continuously innovate by creating creative and engaging content to remain competitive. In addition, rapidly changing social media trends require companies to adapt quickly to digital developments to remain relevant to consumers. Companies must also maintain product quality and service standards because negative reviews circulating on social media may damage brand image and reduce consumer trust. Therefore, effective social media management becomes a critical factor in the success of corporate digital marketing strategies.

Overall, this study demonstrates that social media marketing strategies have a significant influence on increasing sales and strengthening Skintific's brand image. The utilization of content marketing, influencer marketing, live shopping, and active social media interaction enables companies to build stronger relationships with consumers while improving customer loyalty. Skintific's success in leveraging social media proves that digital marketing has become an essential strategy for competing in the modern business environment. Therefore, skincare companies and businesses in other sectors should maximize social media utilization creatively and innovatively to improve competitiveness, expand market reach, and maintain consumer trust amid rapid digital technological developments.

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